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● A new provincial record of *Sinocymbachus quadrimaculatus* (Pic, 1927) (Coleoptera, Endomychidae) from China

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Abstract: *Sinocymbachus quadrimaculatus* (Pic, 1927) is firstly reported from Guizhou Province, China, representing the sixth province of its known distribution. Diagnosis, habitus illustrations and an updated distribution map of this species are provided in the paper.

Keywords: China, Endomychidae, morphology, new provincial record, taxonomy

● 八斑辛伪瓢虫—中国省级新记录（鞘翅目：伪瓢虫科）

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摘要：本文首次报道八斑辛伪瓢虫 *Sinocymbachus quadrimaculatus* (Pic, 1927) 在中国贵州省的分布，这是该种已被记录的第 6 个省份。文中记述的该种附鉴别特征，整体图及分布图。

关键词：中国，伪瓢虫科，形态学，新记录，分类学

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● Introduction

The Asian endemic genus *Sinocymbachus* was established by Strohecker and Chûjô (1970) for *Engonius excisipes* Strohecker, 1943 from Sichuan, China, containing 15 known species from China, South Korea and Vietnam. China represents the core distribution area of this genus: apart from one species only known from South Korea, the other 14 species are all recorded in China (Shockley *et al.* 2009; Chang *et al.* 2020).

When examining specimens of *Sinocymbachus* species, a new provincial record of *Sinocymbachus quadrimaculatus* (Pic, 1927) was recognized from Guizhou Province. As a result, the author decides to report this new record from Guizhou in the present paper.

FIGURE 1. *Sinocymbachus quadrimaculatus* (Pic, 1927), Guizhou: **A** habitus, dorsal view **B** forebody, laterodorsal view in life **C** habitus, laterodorsal view in life. Scale bar = 5.0 mm.

● Material and methods

Specimens examined in this study were deposited in the personal collection of Jia-Heng Chen, Guangdong, China (CCJH). The labels of the specimen are cited verbatim. Detailed information of each label is listed in quotation marks (“”). Individual labels are separated by double slashes (/). Authors’ notes are in brackets ([]). The

habitus photographs were taken using a Nikon D7100 camera with Laowa CF 60 mm f/2.8 2X Super Macro lens. For each final image, several photographs were taken at different focal planes and combined using Zerene Stacker to get one synthesized photograph. The distribution map was made with QGIS 3.28. All images were finally modified and arranged into plates by Adobe Photoshop CC 2019.

● Taxonomy

Sinocymbachus quadrimaculatus (Pic, 1927) 八斑辛伪瓢虫

Fig.1

Amphisternus quadrimaculatus Pic, 1927: 11. **Type locality:** Vietnam, holotype in Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris, France.

Cymbachus quadrimaculatus: Strohecker 1953: 91.

Sinocymbachus quadrimaculatus: Strohecker & Chûjô 1970: 515; Chang *et al.* 2020: 100.

Material examined. 1♂ (CCJH), labeled “Guizhou Province [贵州省], Libo County [荔波市], southwest of Jia’ou Township [驾欧乡西南], 206 Provincial Road [206 省道边], 850m, 2019.VI.10-11. Qiu Lu”.

Diagnosis. Large size, body length 14.0–16.2 mm; elytral patterns composed of four pairs of small round spots, two basal spots located behind humeri, and two apical spots located in apical fourth of the elytron; intercoxal process of mesoventrite with short median ridge at base; ventrite 5 with posterior margin not medially projecting in both sexes.

Distribution. China (Fig. 2): Guizhou (**new record**), Zhejiang, Guangxi, Fujian, Hunan and Hainan; Vietnam: Tonkin.

FIGURE 2. Distribution map of *Sinocymbachus quadrimaculatus* (Pic, 1927) from China: concentric circle: new record in this study; normal circles: previously known records.

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● Additional information

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